

PROCESSES OF MODERNIZATION OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN
UZBEKISTAN AND LEGAL AND REGULATORY BASIS.

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Abstract

From the first years of independence, the development of the education system in our country has been raised to the level of state policy, ensuring that our children acquire modern knowledge and skills in conditions corresponding to world standards, and grow up to be physically and spiritually mature people. Great work is being done to realize the abilities and talents, intellectual potential, to develop the feelings of loyalty and self-sacrifice in the hearts of our youth.

Key words: education, upbringing, value, "Law on Education", continuous education, person, state, society

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's Decision of April 20, 2017 - on measures to further develop the higher education system is significant as it is a logical continuation of the ongoing work on reforming the education system in our country and is aimed at raising it to a new level. One of the most important aspects of the decision is that special attention is paid to the observance of the criteria of international standards in the training of highly qualified specialists, the creation of conditions at its level, and the training of personnel with modern knowledge and skills in accordance with the spirit and requirements.

Therefore, pedagogues working in educational institutions should know how to organize training forms at an optimal level, to enrich the theory of formation of a well-rounded person with various new ideas. Implementing the ideas of the "National Personnel Training Program", ensuring the success of reforms in the education system of our country, depends in many ways on the moral image and professional skills of the teachers working in the education system. .

In the social policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the realization of national identity, the creation of harmony between the individual and the society through the assimilation of national and universal values, the satisfaction of the growth of needs from the private to the general are all the abilities and desires of the young people who are coming of age. It requires research and development of tastes, internal capabilities, unique individual-psychological characteristics. It is impossible to increase the effectiveness of secondary special and higher education without determining the level of formation, mental development, and education of the young generation as a person and subject.

The establishment of the principles of democracy in the infrastructures of the society, in group interpersonal relations, the criteria of equality, subjectivity, cooperation, sympathy (empathy) among citizens becoming a way of life is a vivid expression of the global social-historical victory of the individual world.

In the current era, putting an end to the robotization of the individual, establishing a material and spiritual basis for his manifestation as an independent human (subject), personal worldview (both scientific and religious), stable faith, strong position, firm iy will made it possible to acquire a sharp and inflexible idea. Such a social reality, event, social imagination and need of universal significance means that the recognition of the individual as a central figure and evaluation as a driver of development in our country means that pedagogical knowledge has become a necessity.

In the science of anthropology, it is permissible to establish both the first and the second relationship in the form of human-society and society-human interaction. As Abdulla Awlani predicted in his time: "If pedagogy wants to educate a person in all aspects, then it is necessary to study a person in all aspects."

For the same reason, it is necessary to form a well-rounded person in the process of education, and through its result and product, it is permissible to develop an independent thinker, a creative seeker, a strong-willed, hard-working, ideologically-confident, high-spirited person with a pure conscience.

Because we will not be able to determine the level of upbringing without actually deciding the "subject-subject" relationship. In this place, pedagogy is of great importance.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, said: "If we can educate intelligent, highly moral people, we will be able to achieve our goals, prosperity and development will be decided in our country." It shows that bringing up the new generation who will realize the dream is one of the most important tasks of our state.

In order to fulfill these noble tasks, the Law "On Education" and "National Program of Personnel Training" were adopted at the 9th session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic on August 29, 1997.

A number of factors led to the adoption of the "Law on Education" of the Republic of Uzbekistan: firstly, there was a change in the social system in the environment we live in, and secondly, the attitude towards social production and property changed. , thirdly, the old ideological views did not respond to the new conditions, fourthly, the activities conducted in educational institutions should be organized in accordance with world standards, instilling in students the feelings of national and universal values, and making them well-rounded, deep required training as a knowledgeable specialist.

It is known that the Law "On Education" consists of 5 sections and 34 articles. In the main principles of the state policy in the field of education: education is declared a priority in the field of social development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, so education is one of the main principles of the state policy.

The main principles of the state policy in the field of education:

- that education and training have a humane democratic character;
- continuity and consistency of education;
- compulsory general secondary, as well as secondary special, vocational education;
- the discretion of choosing the direction of secondary special, vocational education;
- that the education system is secular;
- accessibility of education within the framework of state educational standards;
- unified and differentiated approach to the selection of educational programs;
- to be educated and encourage talent;
- harmonization of state and public management in the educational system.

The goal of the reforms implemented in the field of education is to bring up a mature generation.

"First of all, it is necessary to fundamentally change our attitude to the education system. It is necessary that the educational reform be an internal force that will boldly lead us on the path of democratic changes, building a new society, and move all of us. "Let it be clear to each of us like five fingers, or, as the old saying goes, like nine coins, without changing the education system, it is impossible to change people's minds and, therefore, their way of life."

In his many speeches, the president of the country has mentioned the necessity and importance of educational reform.

In the speech of our president at the IX session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 29, 1997, it was stated that the activities carried out so far do not meet the requirements, that we have not been able to completely get rid of the ideological views and distortions typical of the education system from the time of the old Soviets, and secondly, the changes were superficial and did not solve the problems of organically connecting the content and stages of educational and educational processes, i.e. organizing a continuous educational system, thirdly, our the fact that our current educational system cannot meet the requirements of today's modern, developed democratic countries... also showed the need for this reform. In this regard, in his speech on the topic "A perfect generation - the foundation of Uzbekistan's development", the president justified the necessity and factors of reforms in the education system.

The purpose of the Law on Education is to determine the legal basis of education, training, and vocational training for citizens, and to ensure the constitutional right of everyone to receive education.

Section 1 of the Law is called "General Provisions". It expresses the main principles of the state policy in the field of education, the rights to acquire knowledge, to engage in pedagogical activities, the legal status of the educational institution, DTS, the language of education.

Section 2 of the Law "On Education" describes the essence of the education system and its types.

The education system in our republic: state and non-state educational institutions that implement educational programs in accordance with state education standards; Is it a scientific-pedagogical institution that carries out research work necessary to ensure the development of the education system; includes state management bodies in the field of education, as well as enterprises, institutions and organizations belonging to them.

Article 10 of this law states that education is carried out in the following ways.

Section 2, Articles 11-17 of the Law briefly explains the essence of each educational night. As stated in it, pre-school education aims to form a healthy and mature personality of a child, prepared for studying at school. Pre-school education is carried out in state and non-state preschool institutions and families until the child reaches the age of six or seven.

General secondary education is compulsory, and it is carried out at the following levels: primary education (grades I-IV); general secondary education (grades I-IX). Students of general secondary education should receive regular knowledge of the basics of science, the need to acquire knowledge in them, basic educational and scientific and general cultural knowledge, spiritual and moral virtues based on national and universal values. forms skills, creative thinking and conscious attitude to the environment and career choice. "After the completion of general secondary education, a certificate of the type approved by the state is issued, indicating the subjects of education and the grades obtained in them."

The law states that everyone has the right to voluntarily choose the direction of study at an academic lyceum or a vocational college based on general secondary education in order to receive secondary special and vocational education. "Academic lyceums and vocational colleges provide secondary special Vocational education that gives the right to work in the acquired profession and serves as a basis for continuing such work or education at the next level."

In academic lyceums, students have the opportunity to improve their knowledge in the field of study they have chosen and to develop special professional skills aimed at in-depth study of

science. They can continue their studies in certain higher education institutions or realize this skill in their work. Vocational college provides secondary special vocational education within the framework of relevant state educational standards; it allows deep development of students' professional inclination, knowledge and skills, and acquisition of one or more specializations in the chosen profession.

Higher education prepares highly qualified specialists and is carried out in two stages: bachelor's and master's.

The third section of the law is devoted to social protection of the participants of the educational process, which includes issues of social protection of learners and employees of educational institutions, education of orphans and children with physical and mental disabilities. legally expressed.

It is known that the "National Program of Personnel Training" consists of five sections, which include the factors of reforming the personnel training system, the purpose of the program, tasks and stages of its implementation, the main directions of the development of the personnel training system, the program implementation measures are defined. The essence of the national model of personnel training is explained in the 3rd section of the program. The main components of the national model of personnel training are as follows.

"Person" is the main subject and object of personnel training system, consumer of educational services and their implementer. The state policy in the field of personnel training envisages the formation of a well-rounded person-citizen through the continuous education system, which is inextricably linked with the intellectual, spiritual and moral education of a person. In this way, one of the most basic constitutional rights of a citizen, the right to acquire knowledge, to show creative ability, to develop intellectually, and to work according to his profession, is realized.

As a consumer of educational services, a person is guaranteed education and vocational training by the state. In the course of education, a person must fulfill the requirements expressed in the state educational standards. As a provider of educational services, a person, after receiving a suitable level of qualification, engages in teaching the young generation, material production, science, culture and household services in the educational process with knowledge and experience.

Every person is formed as a person only through the system of education, social upbringing and spiritual maturity, vocational training.

As a result, a person's social development occurs - he performs useful functions for society, carefully and creatively understands his tasks and duties, and enters into equal and independent relations with others.

In the personnel training system, the role and role of the individual, rights and obligations are constitutionally strengthened, legally protected and detailed in relevant documents.

"State and society" is the guarantor of personnel training and recruitment, which regulates and controls the activities of the education and personnel training system, and coordinates the activities of educational institutions for the training of highly qualified competitive specialists. .

The state and society shall, for example:

- citizens' right to education, their career choice and professional development opportunities;

- to receive compulsory general secondary and secondary special, vocational education, which gives the right to choose the direction of study at an academic lyceum or vocational college;

- the right to receive information at higher and higher levels on the basis of state grants or on the basis of a paid contract;
financial support of state educational institutions;
- development of public management in order to solve the issues of providing students with study, living and recreation conditions;
social support of the participants of the educational process;
- guarantees the active implementation of regulatory and legal documents in relation to increasing the responsibilities of educational staff, parents for raising children and protecting their lives. Thus, quality professional training, social incentives and protection, assistance in emergency situations are guaranteed by the state.

"Continuing education" is the basis of training of qualified and competitive personnel, including all types of education: preschool education, general secondary education, secondary special education, vocational education, higher education includes education, post-higher education, personnel qualification improvement and their retraining, extracurricular education, DTS, the structure of the personnel training system and its operating environment".

The continuing education system is capable of meeting the various educational needs of people and society, creating wide opportunities for raising the value and status of knowledge, as well as in the conditions of the changing needs of the economy on a general educational, general cultural, professional and scientific basis. specialists should provide basic knowledge and provide social protection of the individual through training.

As directions of continuous education reform, fundamental improvement of the personnel potential of the education system, development of various types of state and non-state educational institutions, from compulsory general secondary education to secondary special, vocational education to ensure its passage, to improve the education management system, to create a system of impartial assessment of the quality of the education process and personnel training, and to expand cooperation with foreign and international organizations related to education and science.

In the radical renewal of the content of science and education, in the preparation of educational standards, educational programs, textbooks and manuals, scientific-methodical. directly participates in the implementation of supply. In addition, science, as a customer in personnel training, achieves a direct balance between scientific research and the educational process.

"Production" is the main customer who determines the need for personnel, as well as the requirements for the quality and level of their training, a participant in the process of providing the personnel training system in terms of finance and material and technical aspects. Performs the functions of customer and consumer in the production personnel training system, actively participates in the process of training, retraining and upgrading of personnel at the required high levels and in the relevant fields.

The needs of production form a social order for personnel training, determine the purpose, task and content of vocational training, promote qualification requirements, determine the conditions for selecting new technologies and forms of training. Production ultimately determines the quality and competitiveness of personnel.

The state and society ensure that the system of continuous education and personnel training is open to all and adapts to life changes. Taking into account the world's advanced experience in the field of personnel training affects all aspects of the continuous education and personnel training system and is one of the factors of its development.

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